

KB Project “Supporting Open Bibliometric Data” (KB OPENBIB): Milestone Summary

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Participating institutions:

Goettingen State and University Library

German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW)

Forschungszentrum Jülich

GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences

Bielefeld University

FIZ Karlsruhe

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Executive Summary

- This internal report describes the status of work in the collaboration project OPENBIB within the Competence Network for Bibliometrics (KB) and provides recommendations for dealing with OpenAlex from 2025. It focuses on the results of the coverage analysis (milestone 2), while also presenting the supporting work of FIZ Karlsruhe in the provision of data as well as the KBMINE project, with a focus on author identification and open access indicators.
- The topic of open bibliometric data is currently gaining importance in scientific research and policy, especially with regard to the open-source database OpenAlex. The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) emphasizes that open data and procedures are essential for future approaches to research evaluation. The French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESR) is promoting the development of an open bibliometrics database based on OpenAlex, with a focus on the French research landscape¹. In France, Sorbonne University and the National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS) have chosen not to renew their licences for commercial bibliometric databases, citing OpenAlex and their open science strategies as the reason². The Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) publicly integrated OpenAlex into the Leiden Ranking at the end of January 2024³.
- There is great interest in open bibliometric data within KB. The “Open Bibliometric Data” user group initiated by the project (jointly coordinated by Dr. Miloš Jovanović, Fraunhofer INT, and Dr. Christian Boulanger, MPI for Legal History and Legal Theory) comprises more than 20 people. The group facilitates the exchange of information on research work, data infrastructure, and interim results of the project. It thus serves as a sounding board for the project work.
- Data provision within KB is carried out by FIZ Karlsruhe. This includes monthly snapshots and a designated version for the project’s data analyses. The development of OpenAlex is very dynamic and new versions can include (breaking) changes and new features. For this reason, there is also the option of versioning queries. FIZ Karlsruhe is supported in its work by the project.
- The collaboratively conducted database comparisons and coverage analyses provided a valuable overview of the strengths and challenges of working with OpenAlex. At the same

¹ <https://www.ouvrirlascience.fr/french-ministry-of-higher-education-and-research-partners-with-openalex-to-develop-a-fully-open-bibliographic-tool/>

² See Financial Times article from 27 December 2023 <https://www.ft.com/content/89098b25-78af-4539-ba24-c770cf9ec7c3> and <https://www.cnrs.fr/en/cnrsinfo/cnrs-has-unsubscribed-scopus-publications-database>

³ <https://www.ouvrirlascience.fr/french-ministry-of-higher-education-and-research-partners-with-openalex-to-develop-a-fully-open-bibliographic-tool/>

time, the analyses illustrate the potential for KB to leverage its expertise on the German research system to improve data quality for its users and third parties in the second half of the project.

- Based on the results, the following recommendations are made for KB:
 - In the future (2025ff), OpenAlex should be integrated into the bibliometric database in parallel with Web of Science and Scopus (hosted by FIZ Karlsruhe) and be assessed via KB's data quality routines ("first class citizen").
 - KB users are encouraged to utilize the substantially increased coverage of publications in OpenAlex in order to unlock this new analysis potential. However, the currently still limited – but greatly improved – data quality in the analyses must be taken into account.
 - The free re-use of OpenAlex data within KB, as well as by third parties, enables new, innovative forms of communication in research, services, data infrastructure, and skills transfer – all of which was previously prevented by the restrictive licences of proprietary data.
 - Further analyses, including comparisons with WoS and Scopus, are required to monitor the improvements in data quality in OpenAlex.
 - At the same time, cooperation with similar national data infrastructures (e.g. France) and OpenAlex must be expanded to avoid the duplication of work (int. governance).
 - Due to the current level of maturity of OpenAlex, it is recommended that the provision of Web of Science and Scopus data is initially continued. If necessary, a breaking point can be defined in three years when OpenAlex and the curation procedures are established.
- This approach is in line with that of the CWTS, which has also announced a transition phase lasting several years.

Kurzdarstellung

- Der interne Bericht beschreibt den **Sachstand der Arbeiten** im BMBF-Verbundprojekt Offene Bibliometriedaten innerhalb des Kompetenznetzwerks Bibliometrie (KBOPENBIB) und gibt eine **Empfehlung zum Umgang mit OpenAlex ab 2025**. Der Schwerpunkt liegt auf den Ergebnissen der Abdeckungsanalyse (Meilenstein 2). Darüber hinaus werden die unterstützenden Arbeiten des FIZ Karlsruhe bei der Datenbereitstellung und des Projekts KBMINE mit Schwerpunkt auf Autorenidentifikation und Open-Access- Nachweise vorgestellt.
- Das Thema Offene Bibliometriedaten gewinnt derzeit in der Wissenschaftsforschung und -politik an Bedeutung, insbesondere die quelloffene Datenbank OpenAlex. Die **Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)** betont, dass offene Daten und Verfahren für zukünftige Ansätze der Forschungsevaluierung unerlässlich sind. Das französische **Ministère de l'Enseignement supérieur et de la Recherche (MESR)** fördert den Aufbau einer offenen Bibliometriedatenbank auf Grundlage von OpenAlex, die sich auf den Wissenschaftsstandort Frankreich konzentriert.⁴ In Frankreich haben zudem die **Sorbonne Université** und das **CNRS** ihre Lizenzen für kommerziellen Bibliometriedatenbanken mit Verweis auf OpenAlex und ihre Open-Science-Strategien nicht verlängert⁵. Das **CWTS** hat OpenAlex Ende Januar 2024 öffentlichkeitswirksam OpenAlex in das **Leiden Ranking** integriert.⁶
- Innerhalb des Kompetenznetzwerks Bibliometrie besteht ein großes Interesse an offenen Bibliometriedaten. Die aus dem Projekt heraus initiierte **User Group "Offene Bibliometriedaten"** (kooperative Leitung Dr. Miloš Jovanović, Fraunhofer INT, und Dr. Christian Boulanger, MPI für Rechtsgeschichte und Rechtstheorie) umfasst mehr als 20 Personen. Die Gruppe dient dem Austausch über Forschungsarbeiten, Dateninfrastruktur und Zwischenergebnisse des Projekts. Die User Group übernimmt damit die Funktion eines **Sounding Boards** für die Projektarbeit.
- Die **Datenbereitstellung im KB** erfolgt durch das FIZ Karlsruhe. Sie umfasst monatliche Snapshots und eine festgeschriebene Version für die Datenanalysen des Projekts. Die Entwicklung von **OpenAlex ist sehr dynamisch** und neue Versionen können Änderungen (*breaking changes*) und neue Features enthalten. Aus diesem Grund gibt es auch die

⁴ <https://www.ouvrirlascience.fr/french-ministry-of-higher-education-and-research-partners-with-openalex-to-develop-a-fully-open-bibliographic-tool/>

⁵ Siehe Financial Times vom 27. Dezember 2023 <https://www.ft.com/content/89098b25-78af-4539-ba24-c770cf9ec7c3> und <https://www.cnrs.fr/en/cnrsinfo/cnrs-has-unsubscribed-scopus-publications-database>

⁶ <https://www.leidenmadtrics.nl/articles/introducing-the-leiden-ranking-open-edition>

Möglichkeit der Versionierung von Abfragen. Das FIZ Karlsruhe wird aus dem Projekt heraus bei den Arbeiten unterstützt.

- Die arbeitsteilig durchgeführten **Datenbankvergleiche und Abdeckungsanalysen** lieferten einen wertvollen Überblick über die Stärken und Herausforderungen bei der Arbeit mit OpenAlex. Zugleich verdeutlichen die Analysen das Potenzial, wie das KB in der zweiten Projekthälfte mit seiner Expertise zum deutschen Forschungssystem die Datenqualität für seine Nutzer und Dritte verbessern kann.
- Die Arbeiten ermöglichten auch die erfolgreiche **Vernetzung** mit Partnern außerhalb des KBs (European Research Council - Policy Unit). Eine von Partnern aus GESIS, SUB Göttingen und DZHW gemeinsam erstellte und kurz zuvor als Preprint (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.16359>) veröffentlichte vergleichende Analyse der Coverage von Referenzen in OAL, WoS und Scopus führte zu einer Einladung zu einem vom französischen Observatoire des Sciences et Techniques (OST) organisierten internationalen Workshop, auf dem außerdem Vertreter von CWTS, Université de Montreal und der MPG vertreten waren. Zudem führte ein Fehlerbericht an OpenAlex zur Korrektur von mehr als 4 Millionen Datensätzen durch den Anbieter, was die Möglichkeiten zur **Partizipation** demonstriert. Im Sinne des Open-Science-Gedankens werden solche wissenschaftsgeleiteten Kurationsarbeiten in der *scientific community* sichtbarer und stärker anerkannt. Für die 112.BiblioCon2024 wurde der Vortrag „Die offene Zitationsdatenbank OpenAlex - ein Gamechanger?“ angenommen, bei dem das Projekt einer breiten Öffentlichkeit präsentiert wird.
- Als Konsequenz aus den Ergebnisse wird **für das KB empfohlen**:
 - **OpenAlex** sollte zukünftig (2025ff) parallel zu Web of Science und Scopus in die Bibliometriedatenbank integriert werden (Hosting FIZ Karlsruhe), die KB Qualitätsroutinen des KB durchlaufen und kontinuierlich kuratiert werden (“first class citizen”).
 - **KB-Nutzer:innen** wird empfohlen, die substanziell vergrößerte Abdeckung von Publikationen in OpenAlex gezielt nachzunutzen, um dieses **neue Analysepotenzial** zu erschließen. Hierbei ist jedoch die aktuell noch defizitäre, aber sich stark verbesserte Datenqualität in den Analysen zu beachten.
 - Die **freie Nachnutzung** der OpenAlex Daten im KB, als auch durch Dritte, ermöglicht neue, innovative Kommunikationsformen in Forschung, Dienstleistungen, Dateninfrastruktur und Kompetenzvermittlung, die bisher durch die restriktiven Lizenzen der proprietären Daten verhindert wurden.

- Weitere **Untersuchungen**, auch im Vergleich zu WoS und Scopus, sind erforderlich, um die Verbesserungen der Datenqualität in OpenAlex zu beobachten.
- Parallel dazu muss die **Zusammenarbeit** mit ähnlich gelagerten nationalen Dateninfrastrukturen (zB Frankreich) und OpenAlex ausgebaut werden, um Mehrfacharbeiten zu vermeiden (int. Governance).
- Aufgrund des derzeitigen Reifegrades von OpenAlex wird empfohlen, **Web of Science und Scopus ab 2025 zunächst fortzuführen**. Gegebenenfalls kann in drei Jahren, wenn OpenAlex und die Kurationsverfahren etabliert sind, ein **breaking point** definiert werden (d.h. mit einer einjährigen Vorbereitungsphase für frühestmöglichen Breakpoint ist eine Lizenzierung für mindestens 4 Jahre mit optionaler Verlängerung vorzusehen).
- Das Vorgehen entspricht dem des CWTS überein, das ebenfalls eine mehrjährige **Übergangsphase** angekündigt hat.

Detailed report: status of work and partial results

WP 1: Database provision

(FIZ Karlsruhe; no funding through KB OPENBIB – support from KB OPENBIB project partners in the “technology” working group)

The OpenAlex snapshots⁷ published each month have been processed by FIZ Karlsruhe within KB’s internal infrastructure since May 2023. Each snapshot is transferred to a PostgreSQL schema. The schema proposed by OurResearch for the data was used as a basis, adapted to KB’s requirements, expanded over time, and updated with each new snapshot. The resulting schema (“raw database”) contains most of the entities, relations, and attributes available in OpenAlex.

A corresponding “bibliometric database” is then created from this schema. To do so, the data are transferred to the structure used for the Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus data. It no longer contains all the content available in the raw data, but rather a selection of entities, relations, and attributes that are of particular interest for KB’s bibliometric evaluations, supplemented by pre-calculated values to simplify the calculation of aggregations, normalizations, and indicators. Making these data available in this structure enables all KB partners to easily access the data and use existing tools and scripts.

The raw data database and bibliometric database thus meet the requirement for maximum data completeness, especially for exploratory use, while also providing simple, well-structured access that is already established within KB. The OpenAlex databases are made available to all users of the KB infrastructure (with the caveat that they have not yet undergone a quality assurance process comparable to that of the WoS and Scopus databases).

For the KB OPENBIB project, the August version (2023) of the raw data and bibliometric database will be retained until the end of the project. Further versions will be deleted regularly when new versions are created, as the available resources are not sufficient to retain all versions. However, for the evaluation of a relatively new data source that is continuously evolving, it is also of great interest to examine the data over time and across versions. To support this type of analysis, selected content and aggregations from all versions are retained in the long term:

- Statistics on selected key figures (e.g. number of rows, non-empty values, distinct values per table for the raw and bibliometric databases)
- A greatly reduced version of the works table (containing the document ID, publication year, DOI, document type, and citation count for each document)

⁷ <https://docs.openalex.org/download-all-data/openalex-snapshot>

- Selected queries are executed for each version and the results are recorded in tables – additional queries that are of interest to users in KB are included so that the results are also available in the following version and are retained in the long term.

WP 2: Database comparison

Overview: coverage with a focus on citation data

(Lead: GESIS, in cooperation with SUB Göttingen and DZHW)

See also: Jack Culbert, Anne Hobert, Najko Jahn, Nick Haupka, Marion Schmidt, Paul Donner, Philipp Mayr (2024). *Reference Coverage Analysis of OpenAlex compared to Web of Science and Scopus*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.16359> [submitted to Scientometrics]

The project work involved creating a comprehensive dataset combining the three bibliometric databases Web of Science, Scopus, and OpenAlex. This dataset was then analysed for overlapping content. The comparison revealed a high number of distinct records in OpenAlex compared to Web of Science and Scopus.

Figure 1: Database comparison – full corpus (left) and the period from 2015 to 2022 (right).

The study also showed that the citation coverage in OpenAlex is comparable to that of WoS and Scopus for recent publication years. In addition, big data analyses supported the identification of structures in the coverage of selected data types.

Document types

(Lead: SUB Göttingen, in cooperation with DZHW and Dr. Alexis-Michel Mugabushaka, policy analyst at the European Research Council Executive Agency (ERCEA))

OpenAlex does not yet offer a differentiated classification of document types. The aim is therefore to develop a semi-automated method for identifying document types within OpenAlex. This approach requires a high-quality reference set containing correctly assigned document types. The reference set can be used to analyse characteristics of different document types, which can in turn support the curation of document types in OpenAlex. To create such a set, publication data from OpenAlex were first compared with the bibliographic databases Web of Science, Scopus, Semantic Scholar, and PubMed. This involved examining the extent to which the publication types and document types differ in the respective databases. Matching types can be used for the reference set. To simplify the cross-database comparison, the document types were reclassified into editorial and scientific contributions (see Table 1). The results show that other bibliographic databases classify more editorial content than OpenAlex (see Figure 2).

Table 1: Example mapping of journal content

Scientific (research discourse)	article
Editorial (editorial discourse)	erratum, editorial, letter, paratext
Types conflicting with publication type (others/none)	grant, book chapter, dataset, book, other, reference entry, dissertation, report, peer review, standard, book series

For the final reclassification of types in OpenAlex, the publication type should first be used (e.g. book, journal, conference proceedings). In the next step, based on available metadata (e.g. number of references, citation count, abstract, number of authors), a semi-automatic method should be applied to determine whether a publication is an editorial or a scientific contribution. Finally, the editorial and scientific contributions should be classified in more detail (e.g. review, specialist article).

Figure 2: Coverage of document types: OpenAlex, Web of Science and Scopus (core publications 2012–2022)

Funding information

(Lead: DZHW)

The availability of high-quality funding information on scientific publications is equally important for stakeholders in science, research funding, and science policy. Until recently, however, these data were only accessible through commercial bibliometric databases, which are associated with high costs. With the emergence of free and open databases such as OpenAlex, these data are now freely available to everyone. During the conceptual phase of the KB OPENBIB project, no funding information was yet available in OpenAlex; this information was only added to the database in May 2023. The first step in our subproject is therefore to analyse the data available in OpenAlex and compare the coverage between OpenAlex and the two commercial databases Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus. This comparison was carried out using the core publications, i.e. the publications that are available in all three databases. The comparison reveals that coverage in OpenAlex still lags considerably behind the commercial databases. Funding information is available in OpenAlex for only about 32 % of

publications that include such information. Furthermore, OpenAlex contributes very little original funding information itself, while the other two databases each provide exclusive information for several million publications. However, this also means that even when using one of the proprietary databases, significant gaps remain. The overlaps in funding information between the databases are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Publications with funding information in the databases

Over the publication years, coverage in OpenAlex steadily improved between 2013 and 2019, reaching a plateau of around 40%. The amount of funding information exclusive to OpenAlex increased only slowly during the same period and remains low.

In preparation for the data curation aspect of our sub-project, an additional comparison with Crossref was conducted to avoid duplicating work on data that are already available. Crossref is one of the largest sources of open bibliometric data and also an important basis for OpenAlex according to its FAQs⁸.

⁸ <https://docs.openalex.org/additional-help/faq>

Figure 4: Availability of funding information in core publications over time. Information from Crossref and commercial providers shows additional funding information that is not currently listed in OpenAlex.

As can be seen in Figure 4, the integration of Crossref data into OpenAlex is not perfect, resulting in a total of 1,771,869 publications with funding information in Crossref that are not available in OpenAlex. Improved data integration could increase the coverage of funding information in OpenAlex by 2.15 % (for German publications, even by 4 %).

The main goal for the remainder of the project is to further close this gap between open and commercial data sources. Our focus is on the German research landscape. We consider three data sources to be particularly promising: final reports of research projects funded by the German Research

Foundation (DFG) and the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF), major publishers, and open access publications.

Journals and publishers

(Lead: FZ Jülich)

To compare journal and publisher data in the three databases, two subsets of data were identified and analysed using different approaches (covering the period 2010–2023):

- a) “Core publications” refer to datasets that are indexed in all three databases. We examined which results were obtained for identical publications in three different sources and how they differed in terms of publishers and journals.
- b) “Margin publications” are only included in one of the three databases. With around 44 million publications, the margin publications from OpenAlex represent by far the largest share of the dataset for the period 2010–2023. They were therefore analysed additionally with regard to the publishers and sources recorded.

database	<i>core publications</i>		<i>margin publications</i>	
	Number of publisher names	Number of source names	Number of publisher names	Number of source names
openalex	2.008	15.474	25.908	117.805
wos	3.478	46.503	1.964	8.618
scopus	3.699	28.827	5.338	29.723

Figure 5:

Despite referring to identical publications, the number of distinct publisher names and source titles differs significantly among the core publications (see Figure 6). A key reason for this is the variation in how data are recorded across the three sources, including different naming conventions and additional spelling variants of journal titles and publishers, even within the same databases. In addition, the extent of name standardization varies across the databases, with OpenAlex applying a particularly high level of standardization for publishers, resulting in a significantly lower number of distinct publisher names compared to WoS and Scopus.

Figure 6:

Publishers

Even after adjusting for different spellings, a cross-database comparison of the largest publishers reveals significant differences in the results. WoS and OpenAlex record significantly more publications for Elsevier than Scopus. Significant differences also exist for the publishers Springer and Wiley. Scopus more frequently accounts for hierarchical publishing structures and, for example, indexes imprints, which leads to a different distribution of publication numbers – namely, to these subordinate brands. By contrast, the publication numbers for the publishers MDPI and Frontiers are almost identical, presumably because they do not have complex publishing structures.

Journals/sources

Despite very clear differences between the three databases in terms of the number of sources, the evaluation of the top journals paints a more nuanced picture: on the one hand, there is a high degree of consistency in the publication figures for some journals when comparing databases; on the other hand, the example of the journal *Physical Review* and its various subseries in OpenAlex illustrates how OpenAlex’s high degree of normalization can lead to problematic results (see Figure 7). Another example is the merging of different journal titles under a current name, which ignores changes in the title over time. Especially when such changes are accompanied by a change in publisher, the historical publishing context can no longer be accurately assessed.

Figure 7

Margin publications

Around 19% of the approximately 44 million exclusive publications in OpenAlex contain no information about their publication sources. A large number of e-book titles stand out, and a great many publications are added to the database via platforms such as arXiv, sometimes with multiple versions of the same publication. An analysis of contribution titles also sheds light on the nature of this additional content compared to WoS and Scopus: a notable share consists of tables of contents and editorial board listings, which are often indexed as contributions and, unfortunately, frequently labelled with the document type “article”. The accurate classification of publication types in OpenAlex is therefore essential for any meaningful representation of scientific output.

To enable meaningful analysis of publication data in terms of publishers and journals, the data must be represented realistically. The merging of variations in spelling is a useful measure for improving the data. In addition, specific bibliometric questions – which take library requirements into account – should be used to determine whether temporal and hierarchical affiliations and changes should be incorporated in future and what options are available for doing so.

Authorships

(Lead: GESIS)

It was found that the overall distribution of authorship data in OpenAlex shows significant and obvious differences compared to Web of Science and Scopus. The similarity between the author lists of Web of Science and Scopus is evident, with a cosine similarity of 0.996, while the cosine similarity of

OpenAlex to Web of Science and Scopus is 0.989 and 0.995, respectively. However, when the relative length of the lists is controlled, the similarities drop to 0.798, X, and X for Web of Science–Scopus, Web of Science–OpenAlex, and Scopus–Web of Science, respectively.

This can partly be explained by the broader scope of OpenAlex, which includes publication types and locations not included in Web of Science and Scopus. However, in the regular meetings we hold with OpenAlex, it has been reported that their author name disambiguation (AND) system requires improvement. In total, OpenAlex lists 68 million unique author names, compared to 35 million and 33 million for Scopus and Web of Science, respectively. However, unlike Scopus and Web of Science, OpenAlex does not contain any null values for authors.

We also found that the current AND system in OpenAlex, which dates from July 2023, causes the overwriting of authorships – particularly affecting Chinese and Spanish names.

Over the course of the project, methods were explored to develop an internal AND system that can be applied to OpenAlex data, including approaches based on natural language processing as well as novel techniques such as those utilizing neural graph networks.

This system uses improved blocking and a graph-based representation that focuses on sophisticated solutions. It is designed as a containerized application that is scalable and can be transferred to the KB infrastructure by the end of the year.

Institutions

(Lead: Bielefeld University)

A comparison between the databases `wos_b_202307`, `scopus_b_202307`, and `openalex_b_082023` using a sample of 5,000 different Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) and the corresponding address-document combinations showed that no “Address_Full” string exists in the OpenAlex bibliometric database (BDB), nor can it be constructed from multiple fields (such as organization name, city, postcode, etc.). This is due to the pre-coding carried out by OpenAlex, which results in a smaller number of different address-document combinations compared to Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus.

A comparison of address-document combinations for a sample publication (DOI: 10.100./JAMAPSYCHIATRY.2019.44910) shows the effects of the curation carried out by OpenAlex. On one hand, mapping at the main institution level standardizes address variants; on the other hand, address strings in OpenAlex that are not assigned to a main institution are not represented in the OpenAlex BDB. For example, there are 33 affiliations for the DOI in WoS and Scopus, while OpenAlex only finds 11 affiliations in the BDB. This affects not only peripheral institutions within the German research system but also larger, well-known organizations such as Philipps-Universität Marburg, University Medical Centre Rostock, the Max Planck Institute of Psychiatry, and Helmholtz Zentrum Munich.

Given these unassigned address strings, a benefit from curation through institutional coding would be expected. Due to the address strings not found in the BDB, it was necessary to deviate from the originally planned approach and use the raw OpenAlex data for the comparison instead. Institutional coding was applied to the address strings in the OpenAlex raw data, and the assignment rates were compared with the current codings for Web of Science (`WoS_b_202307`) and Scopus (`Scopus_b_202307`). The following table shows that the assignment rates are very good and fall within the same order of magnitude as those for WoS and Scopus.

	WoS_b_202307	Scopus_b_202307	Openalex 20230819
Number of distinct addresses	2,269,047	3,449,043	3,955,516
Number of distinct assigned addresses	1,941,829	2,921,426	3,556,325
Percentage of assigned addresses (%)	85.58	84.7	89.91

Number of distinct address-document combinations	7,393,265	6,973,092	7,495,858
Number of distinct address-document combinations assigned	6,887,582	6,173,199	6,705,577
Percentage of assigned address-document combinations (%)	93.16	88.53	89.46
Number of distinct address-document combinations (1986–1995)	663,851	0	558,455
Number of distinct address-document combinations assigned (1986–1995)	609,410	0	472,756
Percentage (%) of assigned address-document combinations (1986–1995)	91.80	0	84.65
Number of distinct address-document combinations (1996–2005)	1,279,831	1,486,303	1,138,750
Number of distinct address-document combinations assigned (1996–2005)	1,202,292	1,289,966	1,011,197
Percentage (%) of assigned address-document combinations (1996–2005)	93.94	86.79	88.80
Number of distinct address-document combinations (2006–2015)	2,374,770	2,640,110	2,488,084
Number of distinct address-document combinations assigned (2006–2015)	2,231,796	2,338,573	2,234,165

Percentage (%) of assigned address-document combinations (2006–2015)	93.98	88.58	89.79
Number of distinct address-document combinations (2016–2025)	2,756,669	2,846,679	3,140,732
Number of distinct address-document combinations assigned (2016–2025)	2,558,988	2,544,660	2,852,471
Percentage (%) of assigned address-document combinations (2016–2025)	92.83	89.39	90.82
Number of distinct documents	4,494,617	4,083,214	4,892,738
Number of distinct documents with at least one assignment	4,265,046	3,709,149	4,366,473
Percentage of documents with at least one assignment (%)	94.89	90.84	89.24

Besides comparing the assignment results, four findings are worth reporting:

Firstly, the ratio between the number of distinct addresses and the number of distinct address-document combinations is notable. For OpenAlex and Scopus, this ratio is almost identical, whereas for Web of Science (WoS) it is significantly higher. This suggests that address-document combinations are more completely represented in WoS than in Scopus and OpenAlex.

Secondly, there are significant differences in the maximum number of characters in the address string. The maximum length is 239 characters for WoS and 1,690 characters for Scopus, whereas the string in OpenAlex has a maximum of more than 24,000 characters. However, very long strings with more than 2,000 characters are only found in a few cases. This affects 530 DOIs. Since the institution coding can handle strings with a maximum length of up to 2,000 characters, the longer character strings were shortened.

Thirdly, there are differences in the performance of institution coding. The runtime for all coding processes is five days for WoS and nine days for Scopus. For OpenAlex, however, the runtime is longer, exceeding 15 days, which is mainly due to the longer address strings. This long runtime may restrict the regular application of institutional coding to OpenAlex.

Fourthly, OpenAlex's curation processes lead to assignment errors. For example, the string "Medizinische Biometrie und Epidemiologie, Universitätsklinikum Hamburg-Eppendorf" (Medical Biometry and Epidemiology, Medical Center Hamburg-Eppendorf) is incorrectly assigned to the company Eppendorf SE, which obviously does not belong to the Medical Center. In addition, the Medical Center Hamburg-Eppendorf does not exist as an institution in OpenAlex. This example suggests that the knowledge about the German institutional landscape embodied in OpenAlex's curation processes is at least partially incomplete.

Next steps

Due to the long runtimes of institutional coding on OpenAlex, a database comparison focusing on publications from 2019 to the present is planned. This aims to reduce processing time and enable a comparison of affiliations and assignment results from the two coding approaches. For this purpose, 346,422 distinct DOIs with all associated address-document combinations were identified across all databases (wos_b_202307, scopus_b_202307, raw_open_alex082023, and open_alex_b_082023). The comparison between the OpenAlex raw data and bibliometric database is still pending in order to be able to draw conclusions about missing affiliations and consequently missing assignments in the OpenAlex bibliometric database (BDB).

To enable a comparison of core and margin document-address combinations, a cross-database identifier was developed based on the DOI and the institution identifier KB_INST_ID, structured as follows:

DOI + symbol (§) + KB_INST_ID = cross-database identifier

-> 10.1007/978-3-7091-8780-7_6§170

Using this identifier, the assignment results of institutional coding can be analysed and compared across databases.

Open access indicators

(Lead: SUB Göttingen)

With the introduction of OpenAlex, the provider OurResearch discontinued the free provision of snapshots from the open access indicator service Unpaywall. Instead, open access indicators are now available in OpenAlex. Coverage analyses comparing OpenAlex with the two proprietary databases Web of Science and Scopus showed a high degree of agreement, which can be explained by the fact that Web of Science and Scopus also reuse data from Unpaywall. When analysing the classification of open access indicators in OpenAlex, an error was identified that affected around 4 million records. After extensive documentation and communication with OpenAlex, this bug has since been resolved. Furthermore, a comparison of open access indicators in OpenAlex using the Semantic Scholar tool was initiated. The analysis revealed differences in terms of open access indicators between the two services, which is why Semantic Scholar will be scrutinized more closely in future studies. For example, approximately 1.7 million full-text links were found for the publication year 2020 that are not included in OpenAlex.

See also: Najko Jahn, Nick Haupka, Anne Hobert (2023). Analysing and reclassifying open access information in OpenAlex. https://subugoe.github.io/scholcomm_analytics/posts/oalex_oa_status/